

fig S4

	4T1			4T07		
	Median	Upper Limit	Lower Limit	Median	Upper Limit	Lower Limit
PDGFRa	22.5	78.4	4.1	30.5	81.1	9.4
PDGFRb	42.8	77.4	17.2	35.0	73.5	5.1
Podoplanin	43.0	83.0	9.7	28.6	72.7	4.5
FAPa	55.8	77.6	26.1	56.7	74.7	20.8
aSMA	22.7	46.6	3.4	11.5	34.3	0.8
CD26	61.5	85.7	26.1	66.2	84.3	12.8